

Interview protocol – Active Window Tracking & Work Characteristics

Study context

This interview is part of a study examining how user interaction data collected from the computer via Active Window Tracking (AWT) reflects daily work characteristics, and how this compares with self-reported experiences and well-being.

Duration: 30-45 minutes

Participants: Individuals participating in the quantitative data collection of this study

Format: semi-structured interviews (online or in person)

Compensation: €20 voucher

Introduction & Consent

Briefly explain the goal of the interview: In this interview, we will look back at a recent work week to discuss your daily work experiences and how these relate to what was (or was not) captured by the tracking tool.

Emphasize:

- Participants may share as much or as little as they feel comfortable
- Don't feel obliged to answer or share any information they don't want to.

Ask for permission to audio record the interview. The recording is used only for transcription and will be deleted when the transcript is complete. All data is anonymized in reporting.

Work week reconstruction

Reconstruct a recent full work week day-by-day

- Can you walk me through your workday on Monday?
Repeat for all days of the week.

If needed:

- What kind of tasks did you work on?
- Were you working from home, office, or elsewhere?

Work characteristics

Throughout describing the workweek, ask questions about the work characteristics measured in the daily survey (changes in work, contact possibilities, independence in work, work variety, interruptions, working overtime, control over start and end times).

Example questions:

- To what extent did you experience [work characteristic] that day?
- What made you experience [construct] in such a way?
- Can you give an example of when you experienced [construct] in such a way on that day?
- What (work) activities contributed to this feeling?
- Was this typical or unusual for you in your work? Why?

Always ask if these activities were performed on the tracked computer, if not mentioned by the participant.

Experience with tracking

How did the participant experience work with the tracking tool installed?

- What was your experience with having a tracking tool installed? How aware are you that your computer activity was tracked by the tool?
- How did it influence your behavior during work?
- How did it affect how you felt during the day?

Closing

Is there anything else you would like to add about your week or the study?

- Thank the participant and explain the next steps (transcription, anonymization, and contact for data collection via daily and weekly surveys)